

Gaps and commonalities in health data access, security and interoperability services

What happens with health data?

Heavy fragmentation, diverse governance, multiple formats...

Aarestrup, F.M., Albeyatti, A., Armitage, W.J. et al. Towards a European health research and innovation cloud (HRIC). *Genome Med* 12, 18 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-020-0713-z>

Some background...

HealthyCloud project

HEALTHYCLOUD
Health Research & Innovation Cloud

- DG RTD Response on H2020 a topic
- HealthyCloud project
 - 5 ERICs + Public Health Institutes + Academy + IT providers
- Outcomes: 5 major services identified

Some more background...

The EHDS and TEHDAS

- DG SANTE response for health data access
- EHDS is a REGULATION
 - Covers primary and secondary uses
 - “Only” for already digitalised health data
 - Clear data governance procedures for data publication, access, processing and results dissemination
 - Data holders, Health Data Access Bodies, Data Catalogues, SPEs, HealthData@EU
- TEHDAS
 - Joint action plan for the implementation of the EHDS

the EHDS

The EOSC Health Data Task Force

- Discussion space created after HealthyCloud in the EOSC ecosystem
 - Supported by the EOSC Association
- Main objectives:
 - Define the EOSC Strategy towards the extensive use of Health Data in research projects through the identification of special requirements, regulations and the ethical and legal grounds to make the access and processing of health data in the context of EOSC fair (e.g., impartial and just) and safe.
 - Foster the interoperability with European Health Data Space for secondary use infrastructure (HealthData@EU) through the identification of common services and formats in the EOSC Nodes arena.
 - Build networks and partnerships mobilising EOSC and EHDS communities.

Where we are...

- Identify stakeholders (HUGE WORK)

Stakeholder/project name	Type of stakeholder project, organization, data space, EHDS entity, ...	Stakeholder details	relevant countries involvem	EOSC	EHDS
EMBL	international organization	hosted in DE	287	x	
Austrian Ministry of Health	Public Body		AT		x
Gesundheits Österreich GMBH (GÖK)	Public Body		AT		x
AT Social Insurance Association (Hauptverband)	EHDS entity		AT		x
Austrian Ministry for Research	Public Body		AT	x	x
Statistik Austria	EHDS entity?		AT		x
ELGA GmbH	national statistic body		AT		x
Local Austrian Hospitals	(personalized) Data Holders		AT		x
Austrian Medical Universities / Reseach Organisations	(personalized) Data Holders		AT	x	x
Spanish Ministry of Health	ministry, public body		ES		x
Spanish Ministry of Science	ministry, public body		ES	x	x
Spanish Ministry of Economy	ministry, public body		ES		x
Instituto de Salud Carlos III	Health research funding authority		ES	x	x
Basque Government Health Department	Public Body		ES		
Osakidetza Basque Health Provider	Public Company?		ES		
Aragon Health Department	Public Body		ES		x
Instituto Aragonés de Ciencias de la Salud	Regional HDAB		ES		x
Valencia Region Health Departmtn (Conselleria de San)	Public Body	Data Holder	ES		x
EUCAIM	EU Project, EDIC candidate	DIGITAL-2022-CLOUD-AI-02, plan	EU		
EHDS board (EHDS)	regulatory body	possibly setting up subgroups, e.g. EU			
SHAIPED	EU project	DIGITAL-2024-CLOUD-DATA-06-H	EU		x
MyHealth@EU	(Former eHDS) infrastructure for primary use		EU		x
HealthData@EUPilot (EHDS2Pilot)	project		EU		x
EOSC-A	AISBL		EU	x	
SIMPL	Cloud-to-edge federations	Procurement of DG-CNECT being	EU	x	x

- Understand the EOSC and EHDS alignment

What we expect...

- Propose effective exchange channels between EOSC and EHDS
- Provide ACTUAL solutions and resources from the EOSC ecosystem to the EHDS ecosystem and reverse
 - FAIRification expertise
 - Cataloguing expertise and showcase
 - Extra “contextual” data (environmental, marine, etc.)
 - Results showcase
 - TREs!! (Well... SPEs!! 😊)

Actions!

- Stay tune for our activities!
 - <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/health-data-task-force/>
- Have your say on SPEs regulation @ TEHDAS2
 - <https://tehdas.eu/public-consultations/>

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